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INITIAL THEORIES ON MODALITY AND DEVELOPMENT HISTORY OF MODALITY

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Annotation. In world linguistics, many scientific studies have been carried out in the field of studying and researching the category of modality. It is important to study psycholinguistic and extralinguistic factors that create this linguistic concept, their specific aspects in different aspects, especially in the comparative aspect of unrelated English and Uzbek languages.

Since the language is studied in an integral relationship with a person and his thinking, worldview, there is a need to study the category of modality in an anthropocentric paradigm. The semantic-structural classification of the modality category, their morphological analysis, the study of hybridization in two languages - English and Uzbek - have not been the object of scientific research.

Key words: modal meaning, declarative modality, performative modality, morphological method, syntactic method, lexical method, category, modal words, modal verbs, object, subject, analytical form, synthetic subject, form (so 'z form), inflectional category, infinitive form, grammatical meaning, auxiliary verb, inversion, sentence semantics, language levels, intonation.

The primary component of sentence semantics, modalities are the fundamental building blocks of sentences. A grammatical-semantic category known as "modality" typically denotes an attitude of the speaker toward the notion being represented or toward the sentence's content. The speaker evaluates this objective reality, contemplates it, and uses a variety of semantic categories to communicate his attitude toward reality.[3] Accordingly, a comparative analysis of the lexical-grammatical characteristics of the modality category in the English and Uzbek languages, revealing the phases of development of the language modality particular to the comparative-historical periods and analyzing them in connection to one another, in the functional aspect 'desire', analysis of the morphological, lexical, and semantic.

One category that has long piqued the curiosity of linguists is the universal category of modality, which is the category unique to all languages. Divergent perspectives exist regarding the scientific-theoretic examination of the modality category within linguistics. Researchers in this field include Sh. Balli, V. Admoni,

E. Gugula, A. Bushuy, A. Bondarko, V. Panfilov, N. Shvedova, I. Rasapov, T. Leontev, V. Vinogradov, F. Palmer, T. Alisova, G. Zolotova, R. Bogatov, and V. Gaklar. They also highlight the significance of modality as a category and the fact that it is the most important sign in speech and speech. They declared. S. Saidov, A. Gulov, R. Ikromova, and Sh. Rahmatullayev are experts in Uzbek linguistics.[4]

The issue of modal logic first surfaced many years ago. Before Aristotle, Protagoras of Abdera—who was referred to as "the most famous, perhaps the first"—was the first to voice a viewpoint regarding modality, or how a speaker views the relationship between their words and reality.[1] Seven centuries later, Diogenes Laertsky wrote in his encyclopedic collection "Lives, Teachings and Wisdom of Famous Philosophers" (2nd and 3rd centuries AD) that "Protagoras spoke in four ways - please, question, answer, command" and mentioned that he called them "speech networks." His work "The Science of Debate" has not survived. According to contemporary linguo-pragmatics, Protagoras' "networks" relate to the broad modal classes of speech acts, which are identified by the speaker's intended meaning for each sentence. Much before the name "pragmatics" was used in Charles Peirce's semiotics, it established the groundwork for linguistic pragmatics, and the study of language communication advanced quickly in modern times.[2]

Professor N. B. Mechkovskaya said that "in the history of communication and language learning, the very idea of diversity and variety of speech, the existence of different goals, methods and styles of communication is considered very important." In this way, the question of how different communication aims (illocutions) might be expressed through speech arose since, up until that point, the speaker was more engaged in the communication process itself than in the vocabulary and grammar of the language.[6]

The foundations of the doctrine of modality were given by Aristotle in his works such as "Analytics", "Metaphysics", "Commentary on Names". In these works, the term "modality" does not appear, Aristotle used the word "enclisis" instead, which he associated with how reliably the speaker calculates his opinion (for example, deriving from a syllogism (conclusion)).

Later, in Greek Alexandrian grammars (2nd century BC) and later in Roman Latin and medieval grammars, the naming of modality with Aristotle's enclisis is the basis for ideas about verb moods, which are understood in different ways according to the relationship of the "tendencies" of the action reported in the speech to reality.[5] It's done. The verb inclination is first defined in an unknown Alexandrian grammar: "Inclination refers to the form of the word that expresses

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the desire (or action) of the mind" (also a similar definition based on the internal form of the term being defined: " Desire is the inclination, desire, desire of the heart (dil).

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